

Blockchain systems: analysis, applications, & risks

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Abstract

A basic blockchain system is characterized as the ordered list for the used nodes and links where these nodes are entitled for storing information and chains connect these links. This technology mainly facilitates the development and management of the availability for the publicly available and required resources and ledger of transactions. This technology also supports the development of the cryptocurrency-based operation and performance evaluation for the technological management. This paper has analyzed different components of Blockchain concepts and evaluated the potential development, structural components, risks, applications within the present-day technological world.

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1. Introduction

Most people recognise blockchain (or, also known as 'BC') as a platform that has gained a lot of popularity lately because of the three main features: decentralisation, immutability, and peer-to-peer (also known as 'P2P'). There are several good real-world challenges it resolves effectively and coherently. BC technology which was envisioned by Ralph Mark in 1979 The vast applicability of BC software can lead to greater uses of cryptocurrencies. Satoshi Nakamoto developed the bitcoin in 2008, and the first cryptocurrency. Several alt-coins, such as Ether (or Ethereum), and Ripple, have been introduced over the years. The BC-based cryptocurrency and its associated implementations are typically labelled as BC 1.0 (the first generation). The alliance between advanced computing systems (BCs) and smart contracts (SCs) is called BC 2. Additionally, outside non-cryptocurrency-specific distributed ledger implementations are generally referred to as BC 3.0 Many different industries have adopted BC 3.0; for instance, BC 3.0 has been used in healthcare (Dinh & Thai, 2018), finance, polling, and the IoT (Ahmed & Askar, 2021; Mohammed & Askar, 2021; Ali & Askar, 2021; Hamad & Askar, 2021). Mainly, BC is a distributed, decentralised, and cryptographically secured database Until written into this ledger database, it cannot be changed or manipulated. Per node in the BC network has a complete copy of the BC. Anything in this economy is handled without the use of a third-party regulator, including transfers and timestamps.

2. Related Works

A. Blockchain Systems

In the most basic form, blockchain is a distributed network that comprises an organised array of different documents that are linked together by connections known as chains (Dinh & Thai, 2018). Only registered users have access to the details stored in these blocks, which pertains to different transactions. User authorization is retained by a dynamic series of self-managed encryption keys: each approved user receives a time-sensitive unique key that auto blocks it if the decryption timer expires (Dinh & Thai, 2018). Without the need for a central authority, blockchain technology allow a distributed computing setting (Husain & Askar, 2021; Samann et al, 2021). Blockchain is a new platform that allows for more autonomous computing. During the meteoric growth of bitcoin as a cryptocurrency in 2017–2018, it grew to popularity. However, cryptocurrency isn't block chain's only application or usage. It has a wide range of uses in businesses, including data collection and sharing in a variety of environments. The aim of this paper is to evaluate the recent literature in the field of blockchain by categorising it and determining the places where potential blockchain study can concentrate in order to stay current with emerging technology.

B. Blockchain Concept

Blockchain is an encrypted distributed public ledger that is stored on a peer node and utilises agreement to verify transactions (Dinh et al. 2018). These principles shape the main meanings of blockchain: decentralisation (Dinh et al. 2018), public ledger, encryption, proof of agreement, peer-of-of-work consensus, and peer-to-to-peer network A ledger is a database of all agency purchases. One solution is to the problem may be a programming file or archive, or even a distributed database like blockchain. It's an inherently unchangeable transaction log unless the rest of the network will monitor the computing capacity, rendering it tamper-proof (or proof-of-of-work-based). The history of the ledger goes back to Mesopotamia about 5000 years ago. When of commodity is entered into a separate list, the oldest and shortest method is known as single-entry accounting. While entry errors are common and undetectable, particularly for family members, fraudulently registered ones, single transactions are nearly impossible to track down. Double-entry accounting introduced a method to balance the books during the year (Dinh et al. 2018). Triple entry bookkeeping, which uses encryption to encrypt

business transactions, was proposed by Mick Grieg in 2005, an attempt to disrupt conventional double entry. Public-key cryptography is used to permanently store and unambiguously record and track non-revocable any transaction, with the three-entry rule of equality to control the sender's authority. Safe contact is characterised as the use of strategies in the presence of adversaries (Sulaiman & Askar, 2015; Fares & Askar, 2016). Through integrating ideas from public key cryptosystems (Gao et al. 2018), blockchain is able to validate user authority, and hashing algorithms helps create network agreement on the blockchain. Diffie Hellman and Hellman first advocated for the usage of public-key cryptosystems for digital signatures an important property of these types of digital signatures is that they can be easily produced by the sender, but impossible for anyone to be forged. But they also they possess other features, such as being a quick and simple way for the sender to get their personal signature, and a user-friendly method for the receiver to verify the message. Two keys occur in public key cryptography (Wang et al. 2018), one called public and one called private, along with an algorithm to return the cipher text to the original plaintext using the private key (Ramezan, & Leung, 2018). Sender or owner produces the public key pair and distributes the private key for verification (Xie et al. 2017); the private key is retained as proof of the authenticity of delivery (Wang et al. 2018). For verification of coins or tokens in a blockchain, this technique is popular. In blockchain, another critical security principle is the one-way hash feature, which converts text strings of arbitrary length into a bit string of constant duration (Xie et al. 2017). Provided a hash function, no matter what input you use, still produces the same hash performance, and no matter how much you modify you make to the initial input, you always have just minor hash change in the end. In the Bitcoin mining process, SHA-256 hashing is used, while in the Ethereum and Litecoin process Ethash and Scrypt are used. Every blockchain uses a consensus algorithm to compromise on the data integrity and integrity of each block with the rest of the network. The most widely-used one is proof-of-of-work. In the P2P network, nodes redistribute the distributed data without verifying it (Perera et al. 2020), and broadcast data on an effort basis of best effort, with nodes allowed to withdraw and enter as they please, embracing the longest proof-of-of-work chain as proof (Sharma et al. 2018). Each node compiles new transactions into a linked data structure with hashes and solves a hard proof-of-of-work problem to add its branch. In this manner (Sharma et al. 2018), the first node to overcome the proof-of-of-work challenge can broadcast a block that includes a proof that she has completed the challenge and provide it to all other nodes on the network to add to the blockchain Only blocks which have pending transactions that haven't been executed will be accepted; approval is signified by operating on the next block with the transaction hashes (Pinna et al. 2018). The bitcoins given to the individual who solved the difficult feature obtain fresh coins.

C. Block Structure

Figure 1. Blockchain structure

Figure 1 is an index and block consists of both a header and transaction data Nonce information (Liu et al. 2018): Previous block hash, time stamp, and nonce: Merkle root hash is a unified transaction hash code for all the block's transactions. If a block has entered the blockchain, there is no way to alter, add, or exclude transactions." If the transaction data is changed, so all nodes in the network will know the new root hash value (Cha et al. 2018). Therefore, if you alter a block's transaction, everybody would know the new root hash. When replacing an entire blocks of text, you can't just choose a different spot; each block is defined by the previous block's hash (Puthal et al. 2018). Presenting a separate blocks in the chain results in inconsistent evidence, as long as the bulk of CPU power is on the network is truthful (Hasan & Salah, 2018). The blockchain is irreversible, if 51% of the power is owned by malicious actors. E-cash transfers can be executed on the network, although the blockchain is an example of a distributed ledger technology (Abdulkahleq & Askar, 2021; Khalid & Askar, 2021). For this to be understood, see in Fig. 2, we must differentiate between centralised, decentralised, and dispersed (Qu et al. 2018). Centrifugal and decentralisation describe control and dispersion as both "levels of influence," whereas position relates to physical location (Wei et al. 2018). Power is placed in the hands of a particular authority in a central government, but is dispersed to many separate ones in a decentralised one. a non-global structure; a distributed system is spread through several points. Decentralization may take two forms: centralised or dispersed (Ren et al. 2018). As far as computing resources are concerned, a cloud provider will be more widely distributed, but power will be centralized (Xia et al. 2017). Decentralized and distributed blockchain like Bitcoin and Ethereum are novel models of the kinds of public and private blockchain networks that will emerge in the future (Mencias et al. 2018). As a result, bitcoin and Ethereum are resistant to interference from any one party, which makes it a decentralised, and blockchain evidence can be mirrored through multiple individual nodes worldwide, creating a global framework of consensus (Qu et al. 2018).

Figure 2. Distributed, decentralized and centralized networks

Tree authentication was first conceived as a way to save memory and easily prove that a chosen attribute is right. Merkle trees are essential to the functioning of blockchain. It is, in theory, feasible to construct a non-Merkle tree blockchain, but doing so comes with major scalability challenges that prevents them from being used by anything but the most efficient computers in the longer term. A Merkle tree where each node is a leaf, derived from its two daughters, and where the depth of each node is proportional to the height of the subtree (that is, depth of its parent is 2, intermediate node = 1/2 of their sum). Instead of creating a merkle trees directly from transaction data, Bitcoin hashes transaction data, recursively up to the root before a merkle block is found, which is then preserved as a reference to that points to it. as is seen in the illustration below, once a transaction at the base of the data structure changes, the root hashes spread to the various locations in the structure and provide different hashes (Liu et al. 2018). Thus, if one of the structures changes, the root hashes (Ren et al. 2018) will no longer be matched to the hashes on it, and the data is changed, a different data structure and an entirely new root hash will arise (Cha et al. 2018). Honest nodes can deny those fraudulent blocks, as long as the rest of the network remains (Hammi et al. 2018). The Bitcoin proof-of-of-

of-work algorithm distributes hashing power so evenly among all connected nodes (Cha et al. 2018), thus it cannot be outpaced by malicious nodes with more processing power, even if it uses several CPUs (Hammi et al. 2018). The consensus of other blockchain is like the proof-of-work algorithm described in the following.

3. Methodology

Methodological components are vital for assessing the reliability and validity of a research. In this research, positivist philosophical approach has been selected. Based on the assessment, potential keywords such as blockchain, blockchain system, risk, application etc. have been used in terms of different determiners such as AND, OR, BUT etc. Only the articles published between 2015 and 2021 had been selected without any major exception. Databases such as SCI and SSCI have been used in this research mainly to discuss on the research findings. Data deletion method has been used partially to refine the collected data.

4. Results and Analysis

A. Blockchain Framework

The concept of a blockchain which contains a distributed ledger, a cryptographic scheme, and a smart contract (Dinh et al., 2018). Blockchain frameworks can be used in the SCI/S&CIF Below, we present the results. BlockBench is built on prior knowledge of conventional blockchain technology and offers a quantitative platform for evaluating and comparing private blockchain (Dai et al. 2018). Crypto-currency, security settlement, and several other useful financial features are all packaged in the application layer. The middle layer comprises features, including the consensus engine, data model, and executable contracts reside on the blockchain (Sakakibara et al. 2018). The Processor, the disc, and the network are at the lowest floor. At the framework layer, we have the Blockchain, and then the execution engine, the data model, and the consensus. Think of the programme layer as a deal (Guo et al. 2018), the execution engine as a mainframe, and think of a virtual machine as a laptop or personal compute (Sakakibara et al. 2018). In other words, the block transaction model is used for analytics, and for determining agreement (Dai et al. 2018), while the latter two layers are PoW, PoS, and PBFT are used for generating commitments. Blockchain, on the other hand, though, is met with controversy due to each node's transaction needing to be stored in each other nodes' records (Guo et al. 2018). Slowing down not only decreases the number of nodes (Sakakibara et al. 2018), it also reduces the amount of time it takes to make transactions on each network (Dai, Zhang, Wang, & Jin, 2018). the authors offer an NCSF platform: A distributed storage network storage framework, referred to as the N-DS system, deals with this problem (Cai et al. 2018). There is also a kind of integrated database that is integrated into blockchain networks. Any new created block is further partitioned into six sub-blocks, which is then sub partitioned to three equal length sub-blocks (Guo et al. 2018). This is after the splitting of the blocks based on a system of properties. Blockchain provides the end to end re-to-end unravelling mechanism, in which subsequent nodes are decoded prior to standard unravelling. In other words, here we have eliminated the key block, hence the bloat issue has been solved Keys, such as WANG, Zhang, and Zhang (2018) on the other hand, talk about that even though the platform as NC-DS solves the problem of storage, there is a critical component missing: confidence. The authors use modern IFS attribute-based encryption technologies, Ethereum blockchain, and a shared storage infrastructure to monitor data access with detail in distributed systems (Barnett & Treleaven, 2017). There is only one authority for a person's records, and no one else can give out a hidden key to share it. This structure is more versatile than the conventional. In comparison to Dai et al. (2018), the investigation of the reduction of fat nodes shows that Yuan, Xu, and Si (2017) had a different approach. They proposed a scheme that makes use of the aggregate signature to preserve anonymity. Many privacy-preserving blockchain

implementations use a large block data storage capacities. The benefit of distributed ledgers is that they permit more than one block to preserve their own, so a reduction in block bloat is needed (Barnett & Treleaven, 2017). According to the signature aggregation mechanism, storage space may be reduced. This scheme accomplishes its task by obscuring the number of transactions required to complete an encryption and decryption. The signature on a contract doesn't increase based on the amount of inputs, which allows for more efficient processing. as a database to monitor the social and cognitive capital (social/cognitive capital-distributed ledger) (compute identity management framework), "to trace individuals' socially-given characteristics as well as their intellectual capital and help handle this in a decentralised manner" (DLT). This idea of self-sign able identification and distributed trustworthy identity was used in Utopia and DLT formulas are derived from these three schemes.

B. Algorithm used in Blockchain System

A significant amount of attention has been put on applying the variety of possible technologies and techniques to blockchain as a result. Multi-Integrated Evolutionary Research in Linear Algorithm (Liang et al., 2017); Research on the Effects of Multi-Linked Data on Scalable Algorithms (Gao et al., 2018) (Huang et al., 2017). Here are 3 journal papers discussing the most important concepts related to blockchain algorithms. It is crucial to keep the chain's verifiability factor and creation of a uniformity in any blockchain network. Standard clustering is unable to sustain the network's authenticity in this instance. The activity pattern-clustering algorithm of Huang et al. uses sequence data to organise nodes into groups. It was developed using a calculation of sequence similarity and clustering. Euclidean, DTW, and LCSS similarity measures are included. Crypto. Wu, Shi, Zhao, and Zheng (2018) used a Post-Quantum algorithm to secure the blockchain network against external attacks and make it consistent (Sakakibara et al. 2018), while preserving trustworthiness. Randomness and pre-image resistance were built into the lattice algorithm. The first and last sign elements of the algorithm are incorporated into the architecture of the algorithm itself (Dai et al. 2018). Finally, Li et al. (2017) also suggest an algorithm which utilises novel multilink distributed computing. This algorithm claims to reduce validation time while still the degree of confidence in distributed ledgers (Hassani et al. 2018). The algorithm makes use of the principle of connection degree and node confidence to ensure good communication within a group of nodes. The overall concurrency is increased, as well as the connectivity and coordination performance The nodes are tagged into the categories of truthful node, victim node, free rider node, and attacker node (Kshetri & Voas, 2018). Tasks of these nodes are defined as follows: An active node gets the data, while a free node is prohibited from forwarding the data. Each node is assigned a confidence value between .8 and 1; ineffective nodes have values between .8 and .6, and free riders have values less than .6. Active nodes are situated at the peak of the contact chain, while freeloaders can be found at the base and tricksters in the leaves (Kshetri & Voas, 2018). Therefore, transferring details without risking nodes acting dishonestly gets the information to those that have it first. In brief, all three algorithms are built to preserve the verifiability and decentralisation, but even the most private one is concluded to be a harmful. Also if the degree of correlation with other users in the network has been calculated, a multi-linked-integrated connection algorithm increases the risks so there are degrees above which would stay as a trusted nodes that do not become bad actors.

C. Application of Blockchain

Bitcoin was created to correct the electronic cash's electronic double-spending issue in a decentralised setting With most people, blockchain technology's first and most interesting use

is electronic currency (Kim & Jeong, 2018). With the immutability and decentralisation of the distributed ledger technology and the blockchain, people have come to understand that it's possible to configure and use them for other applications like smart contracts, land registries (Hassani et al. 2018), e-voting, e-commerce, and supply chain management. Additionally, given so much research and development has been done on implementations of blockchain, new projects are still arising (Huang et al. 2017; Askar, 2017; Fizi & Askar, 2016; Askar, 2016; Keti & Askar, 2015; Qadir & Askar, 2021). Fat protocols and thin protocols can also be included when we address blockchain applications (Askar et al., 2011; Al Majeed et al, 2014;Aste et al. 2017). A protocol is a widely agreed-upon compilation of procedures and processes, which can be used to develop programmes (Kim & Jeong, 2018). At every phase of the project, we've established specific rules and guidelines. Creative saying:At present, the key distinction between the Internet and Blockchain is on the protocol layer. The internet's whole structure is built on protocols like TCP/IP, HTTP, IMAP, and the like. Since the internet is built on TCP/IP, the Web is built on HTTP, and HTTPS, and because of that, email functions as well. Such an open set of protocols allows a great variety of various programmes to connect with one another, bringing unparalleled benefit (Kim & Jeong, 2018). Although the public protocols seamlessly provide the means of doing so, the generated value is captured by application software. The importance Facebook, Twitter, and the two others make use of transparent protocols (Aste et al. 2017), but catch just a small profit. This means that when you buy into software, you earn high profit, but when you invest in protocols, you lose money. Due to the volunteer effort required to run their infrastructure, several of the internet's free protocols are still sustained by non-profit organisations. The way the internet is built is made up of thin protocols and richly applied is with well-crafted software. Blockchain stack, meanwhile, features fat protocols in terms of utility capture (Lee, 2018). The vast majority of the importance is present in the transparent protocol layer, and only a small amount of it is made available for individual clients at the implementation layer One can learn the significance of the market capitalization of two famous networks, Bitcoin and Ethereum, by considering them two metrics: the former is market capitalization of Bitcoin and the latter for Ethereum. While the Bitcoin has a market capitalization of \$200 billion USD, the most well-name businesses based on various blockchains like Coinbase have just tens of billions of dollars in their own value. At the time of writing, ETH has a market capitalization of \$30 billion and apps created on top of that hasn't made any return yet. Token exchanges, including Binance, designed on top of Ethereum, have the most valuable tokens priced at \$4 million and \$1 million respectively (Li et al. 2017). Thus, it is obvious that the protocol layer added considerable value by capitalising on blockchain principles. What contributed to collecting meaning at the layer above the protocol was, these were mutual data and cryptographic tokens. In the first place, the decentralised data layer on blockchain eliminated constraints, and allowed for any number of independent apps to be built with unrestricted access to data (Lee & Lee, 2017). The more details an internet-based programme used to collect on a particular sector, the more their partners or new rivals is required to allow to access it. Moving from one cryptocurrency platform to a to a newly discovered one is much of the challenge of shifting from Gmail to a different email service when the data is long-term at a centralised data source. An open protocol imposes additional costs on the consumer which necessitates the market to find ways to lower costs, which makes room for innovative goods to be created. Also, economic incentives offered in the form of cryptographic tokens are essential for both growth and acceptance of blockchain protocols. The concept of blockchain supports the issuance of cryptographic tokens on top of an established blockchain or as a different blockchain component, depending on the project. [The Modern blockchain protocols and applications] will now collect money by means of their own creation, typically issuing cryptographic tokens in addition to funds for expansion. To incentivize app contributions, cryptographic tokens may be the preferred mode of payment, as well as the distribution

process. The worth of the currency increases in relation to the performance of the company. Stakeholders of the project work often contribute to promotion and development of demand, since they have already been the ones who made a lot of money on it. It's currently capped and locked at a token supply that will be generated for a certain period of time and a certain cost (Huang et al. 2018). The tokens are small in number, which could contribute to token price inflation. In other words, this appreciation is only beneficial to the developers of the blockchain programme (Kim & Jeong, 2018), so they are able to sell the tokens they already had, while the price is greater, whereas other people assume that there will be more demand in the future. they saw that this as a great opportunity for more expansion and they expected that they would get much further profits if that if more people begin to appreciate the importance of the programme, more people will be drawn to it, and others new to the platform will choose to participate in the protocol In the future (Kim & Jeong, 2018), the mining process could keep running in a loop, seeking new value from newly minted cryptocurrencies.

Figure 3. Value captured and analysed on Protocol and application layer for Blockchain. This has meaning since the market capitalization of the initial protocol increases much more rapidly than the total valuation of the implementations developed on top of it. as discussed (Huang et al. 2018), the underlying mutual data layer results in value being generated in protocol layer (Li et al. 2017), while the aggregated layer yields large numbers of values in the internet. Figure 4 thus represents a fat protocols supported by mutual data and cryptographic tokens.

5. Conclusion

Distributed public database, consensus process, non-based on trust, consensus Also, the paper identified the most commonly used consensus algorithms for blockchain. As mentioned above, we assume that permissioned blockchain may be deployed using either open or closed platforms. For the same purpose, blockchain system has influenced the internet on protocol but not in the application layer. Speculations were made about the future and how it could have many blockchain-based technologies (Alabi, 2017) including smart contracts, registries of titles, and automated voting. Overall, the paper provides a simple explanations of the core elements of blockchain, how it was created, who invented it, how it functions, how it is used, and potential implementations and problems. This research will be developed and refined depending on the audience's needs.

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